

Supporting information

Self-Trapped Exciton Emission Under Ambient Conditions in Lead-Free Two-Dimensional Halide Double Perovskites Triggered by Heterovalent Metal Substitution

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Experimental Section

The preparation of precursors and growth of perovskites were conducted in an argon-filled glove box due to the moisture instability of halide salts. The water and oxygen levels are less than 0.01 ppm during the experimental process.

Chemicals and materials

n-Propylammonium bromide (PABr, $\geq 98\%$), silver bromide (AgBr, 99%), indium bromide (InBr_3 , 99.999% trace metals basis), manganese bromide (MnBr_2 , 98%), bismuth bromide (BiBr_3 , $\geq 98\%$), silver iodide (AgI, 99%), toluene (anhydrous 99.8%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, anhydrous $\geq 99.9\%$), were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. n-Propylammonium iodide (PAI, $\geq 98\%$) was purchased from Greatcell Solar Materials Pty Ltd. Manganese iodide (MnI_2 , 99.9% metals basis) and indium iodide (InI_3 , 99.999% trace metals basis) were purchased from Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd. Propylamine hydrochloride (PACl, $\geq 98\%$) was purchased from Tee Hai Chem Pte Ltd.

Precursors of $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgBiBr}_8$ and $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgInBr}_8$

PABr (140 mg, 1 mmol), AgBr (46.94 mg, 0.25 mmol) and BiBr_3 (112.17 mg, 0.25 mmol) were dissolved in 1 mL DMSO. Similarly, PABr (112 mg, 0.8 mmol), AgBr (37.55 mg, 0.2 mmol) and InBr_3 (70.91 mg, 0.2 mmol) were dissolved in 1 mL DMSO.

Precursors of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$

Different amounts of Mn halide were used for each precursor with the same concentration of 0.2 M. Take x as 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6, respectively. PABr (112 mg all the same), AgBr (33.78, 30.03, 26.28 mg), MnBr_2 (8.59, 17.18, 25.76 mg), and InBr_3 (63.81, 56.72, 49.64 mg) were dissolved in 1 mL DMSO respectively.

Precursors of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.4}\text{In}_{0.8}\text{I}_y\text{Br}_{8-y}$

Different halides were used for each precursor with the same concentration of 0.2 M. Take y as 2, 4 respectively. PABr (56, 74.76 mg), PAI (0, 149.52 mg), AgBr (30.03 mg both), MnBr_2 (17.18 mg both) and InBr_3 (56.72 mg both) were dissolved in 1 mL DMSO respectively.

Synthesis of 2D double perovskite films

All precursors were stirred for over 3 hours in glass vials until complete dissolution was observed. All substrates, including glasses and silicon wafers, were cleaned sequentially in DI water, ethanol, and acetone, followed by the UV-Ozone cleaning for 10 minutes. The perovskite films were deposited by a one-step spin-coating process. Perovskite solutions were dropped on the substrate followed by the dropping of toluene as the antisolvent for 50 seconds. Antisolvents

are usually employed to facilitate perovskite nucleation to obtain a more uniform film with fewer pinholes. Toluene was dropped on the center of the substrate at 30 seconds, and the amount was five times that of the perovskite solutions. The spinning rates and acceleration rates were varied to investigate their influence on film morphology. The obtained films were annealed at 80°C (bromide samples) or 50°C (iodide mixed samples) for 5 minutes on a hot plate.

Materials characterization

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns was measured by a Bruker D8 advance X-ray diffractometer operated at 40 kV voltage and 40 mA current with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=1.5406$ Å). Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images were taken by a JEOL JSM-7610F Plus scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS) analyzed at 15 kV. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) characterization was carried out using a Bruker Dimension ICON microscope with the mode of tapping in air with standard. UV-Visible spectra were collected on an Agilent Cary 5000 and Shimadzu SolidSpec-3700 spectrometer. The samples were spin-coated on the quartz glasses for characterization. The Raman measurements were performed on a Renishaw inVia spectrophotometer using a dual laser system with the excitation wavelength of 532 and 325 nm. The detector is Renishaw CCD and the grating is 1800 g/mm for Raman characterization. Steady-state PL for Figure 2d, temperature-dependent PL, and time-resolved PL measurements were conducted on a Princeton Instrument HRS-750 spectrograph with Pylon 100BR eXcelon CCD. The grating is 300 g/mm, and the excitation wavelength is 449 nm. The PL spectroscopy for Figure 4c were performed using a JY Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution Raman spectrometer in the backscattering geometry with a 514.5 nm Lexel SHG 95 argon ion laser. The samples were spin-coated on the silicon wafer for characterization.

Table S1 Interplanar distance of (001) crystal plane

Sample	2θ (°)	d (nm)
Mn_{0.2}	7.209	1.225
Mn_{0.4}	7.205	1.226
Mn_{0.6}	7.185	1.229

Table S2 SEM-EDS results of **Mn_{0.2}**, **Mn_{0.4}**, and **Mn_{0.6}**

Sample	Element	Atomic ratio at		
		Location 1	Location 2	Location 3
Mn_{0.2}	Mn	0.212	0.193	0.324
	Ag	0.920	0.851	0.916
	In	0.868	0.955	0.760
Mn_{0.4}	Mn	0.493	0.534	0.596
	Ag	0.837	0.785	0.809
	In	0.670	0.552	0.595
Mn_{0.6}	Mn	0.493	0.534	0.596
	Ag	0.837	0.785	0.809
	In	0.670	0.552	0.595

Tables S3 Optimized synthesis parameters corresponding to the best-quality films

Sample	Concentration (mol/L)	Spinning rate (rpm)	Acceleration (rpm/s)	Annealing temperature (°C)
Mn_{0.2}/Mn_{0.4}/Mn_{0.6}	0.2	4000	500/500/2000	80

Figure S1. (a) Out-of-plane XRD patterns of $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgBiBr}_8$ through $2\theta/\omega$ scan mode (b) $2\theta/\omega$ scan of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ from 5 to 40° with different Ψ angles

Figure S2. (a) SEM and (b) AFM image of $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$ (c) SEM and (d) AFM image of $\text{Mn}_{0.6}$

Figure S3. Tauc plot derived from the absorption spectrum of (a) $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ and (b) $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.4}\text{In}_{0.8}\text{Br}_{8-y}\text{I}_y$. Here, a direct band gap is assumed.

Figure S4. Optical absorption spectra for $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{0.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Br}_8$ ($\text{Mn}_{1.2}$) and $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{0.3}\text{Mn}_{1.4}\text{In}_{0.3}\text{Br}_8$ ($\text{Mn}_{1.4}$) with higher Mn amount

Figure S5. (a) Summary of temperature-dependent PL spectra for peak 2 of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ integrated in the same figure and (b)-(h) corresponding PL mappings from 4 to 300 K within the same $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ area. In panel (a), for each temperature, the colored region represents the upper and lower emission intensity. The dark solid lines represent the average curves, which will be used in the following curve fitting process.

Figure S6. (a) Summary of temperature-dependent PL spectra for peak 1 of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ integrated in the same figure and (b)-(h) corresponding PL mappings from 4 to 300 K within the same $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ area.

Figure S7. (a)-(b) Original average steady-state PL spectra of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ with light scattering effect in the temperature range of 4-300 K. The fitted peaks with Gaussian line shape are plotted in dash lines. Curve fitting parameters are listed in the tables below. The emission spectra display minor peaks around 631 and 635 nm ascribed to indoor light scattering. These peaks were smoothed in Figure 2d for better identification.

Figure S8. Temperature-dependent integrated PL Intensity of (a) peak 1 and (b) peak 2 for **Mn_{0.4}** with corresponding fitted curves

Figure S9. Power-dependent integrated PL intensity@4 K for **Mn_{0.4}** with corresponding fitted curves